

Calculation of land surface temperatures using Landsat 8 satellite data for near-surface geothermal 3D modelling

Björn Holstein, Thorsten Agemar, Muhammad Anees, Jens-Olaf Delfs, Tom V. Schintgen
LIAG Institut für Angewandte Geophysik, Deutschland

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Abstract

The work presented here was carried out as part of the WärmeGUT project, which supplements the Geothermal Information System (GeotIS) with information on near-surface geothermal energy. This is a digital geothermal information system that shows the potential and locations of deep geothermal energy in Germany. Complex and heterogeneous data sets from various sources serve as the basis for calculations. Part of this data is knowledge of the average land surface temperatures (LST), which is essential for estimating the near-surface geothermal potential. The data from the German Weather Service provides an important basis, but does not have sufficient spatial resolution. A study was conducted to determine whether the use of satellite data could improve data quality. It has been shown that Landsat 8 satellite data provide very good results in terms of spatial resolution, but this is offset by moderate temporal resolution. Therefore, tests were carried out to determine whether the inclusion of additional satellite data would ultimately result in the generation of an LST map that combines both good spatial and temporal resolution.

1. Introduction

An accurate 3D temperature model is a prerequisite for the successful installation of near-surface geothermal systems (Agemar et al. 2012). An important part of the calculation of this model is the land surface temperature, as surface temperatures influence soil and rock temperatures down to a depth of approximately 15 metres.

Until the end of 2025, GeotIS used a surface temperature map based on measurements from 712 weather stations (air temperature 2 metres above ground level from 1961 to 1990) in combination with an elevation model.

Due to the low density of the reference points, which are distributed more or less evenly across Germany, the DWD's surface temperature map has a low resolution of 1000 m, which, despite being enhanced by the elevation model, only results in a final LST map with limited detail accuracy.

As part of the WärmeGut project, a Germany-wide LST map with a higher resolution has now been calculated. This map also covers the border areas of neighbouring countries.

2. Methods

In the first phase of the project, data research was conducted to find higher-resolution LST data. This research revealed that, although there is no final product that offers significantly better resolution than the DWD data, raw satellite data can serve as a starting point for creating a high-resolution LST map with average values for a desired period of time from a defined area.

Landsat 8 satellite data in particular has a higher spatial resolution (genuine 100 m), but a series of steps are required to obtain the temperatures from the sensor values. The two sensors, OLI

(Operational Land Imager) and TIRS (Thermal Infrared Sensor), record 11 bands, of which the following bands are relevant for LST calculations:

	<u>Band</u>	<u>Name</u>	<u>Wavelength (μm)</u>	<u>Application</u>
•	4	Red	0.64 – 0.67	vegetation, landcover
•	5	NIR (Near Infrared)	0.85 – 0.88	vegetation, biomass
•	10	Thermal Infrared 1	0.60 – 11.19	surface temperature

The Landsat 8 dataset was downloaded from the website of the Earthexplorer section of the USGS (United States Geological Survey). To cover Germany, the corresponding tiles (figure 1) result in a total of over 9000 individual images. A comprehensive documentation of the data and the recording process was provided by the USGS (Ihlen 2019).

Figure 1: Tiles (coverage areas) with paths and rows of the Landsat 8 satellite in the area of Germany.

The LST was calculated using satellite images taken between 2013 and 2024.

The calculation requires the application of a series of equations using procedures that can recalculate raster image data. In this case, ArcGIS pro software was used. A calculation method based on Avdan & Jovanovska (2016) taking into account scientific findings of Li et al. (2023) and Sobrino et al. (2004) was applied.

The processing, which comprises six steps to establish a specific relationship between the thermal band data set and metadata information, was carried out using batch processing in the ArcGIS ModelBuilder. To ensure a reliable LST calculation, cloud cover was removed using the ArcGIS tools Reclassify and Minus. The final result is a high-resolution (30 m) LST map of Germany.

2.1 Description of the individual steps

A graphical overview of all calculation steps is shown in Figure 2.

1. Conversion of digital numbers (Band 10) to Top of Radiance (TOA) L_λ

$$L_\lambda = ML \times Q_{cal} + AL - O_i$$

L_λ = TOA spectral radiance ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot sr^{-1} \cdot \mu m^{-1}$)

ML = Radiance multiplicative scaling factor (gain) from MTL/Metadata*

AL = Radiance additive scaling factor (bias) from MTL/Metadata

Q_{cal} = Quantized and calibrated standard product pixel values (DN) within Band 10.

O_i = correction factor Band 10 = 0.29

*The Rescale factors are included in the product METADATA (MTL) downloaded with the dataset.

2. Conversion of TOA Radiance to Brightness Temperature (BT)

$$BT = \frac{K_2}{\ln\left(\frac{K_1}{L_\lambda} + 1\right)}$$

The inverse Planck constants K_1 and K_2 from the MTL are used.

3. Calculation of the NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)

The NDVI is a spectral vegetation index derived from measurements of relatively narrow wavelengths of reflected light (10 to 50 nanometres) in the electromagnetic spectrum. The basic principle is that the visible red band is absorbed, while the NIR (near infrared) is reflected. This allows the proportion of vegetation and the type of vegetation to be taken into account.

$$NDVI = \frac{(NIR - RED)}{(NIR + RED)}$$

Band 5 (NIR) and band 4 (RED) of the Landsat 8 data are used.

4. Compute Land Surface Emissivity (ϵ)

Land surface emissivity (LSE) is a physical property of the Earth's surface that describes how efficiently a surface emits thermal energy in the form of long-wave radiation (infrared radiation). Emissivity (ϵ) is the ratio of the actual thermal radiation emitted by a surface to the radiation of an ideal black body at the same temperature.

The calculation is performed in two steps, first calculating the vegetation fraction (Pv)

$$Pv = \left(\frac{(NDVI - NDVI_{min})}{(NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min})} \right)$$

Figure 2: Flowchart displaying all steps for processing LST data from Landsat 8 satellite pictures.

The PV is then incorporated into the second formula.

$$\varepsilon = 0.004 * PV + 0.986$$

Where ε = Land surface emissivity
 0.986 corresponds to a correction value of the equation

5. Land Surface Temperature (LST) calculation

Land surface temperature (LST) is the radiation temperature calculated based on the brightness temperature of the upper atmosphere, the wavelength of the emitted radiation and the emissivity of the land surface.

$$LST = \frac{BT}{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda \times BT}{p}\right) \ln(\varepsilon)}$$

BT = brightness temperature (from Band 10)
 λ = wavelength of emitted radiance ($\approx 10.895 \mu\text{m}$ for Band 10)
 $p = \frac{h \times c}{\sigma} = 1.438 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mK}$
 ε = emissivity

2.2 Cloud filtering

Once the LST has been calculated for all individual images, the cloud cover must be filtered out of each image to avoid obtaining distorted LST values. To do this, the QA (Quality Assessment) files with cloud information (see table 1) associated with the band files are downloaded, the shadow is included and saved as a simplified version, which provides a mask for cutting out the cloud portion from the generated LST tiles. The cutting procedure is done by the ArcGIS Minus tool.

Pixel Value	Fill	Dilated Cloud	Cirrus	Cloud	Cloud Shadow	Snow	Clear	Water	Cloud Conf.	Cloud Shadow Conf.	Snow/Ice Conf.	Cirrus Conf.	Pixel Description
1	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	None	None	None	None	Fill
21824	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Low	Low	Low	Low	Clear with lows set
21826	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Low	Low	Low	Low	Dilated cloud over land
21888	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Low	Low	Low	Low	Water with lows set
21890	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Low	Low	Low	Low	Dilated cloud over water
22080	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Low	Low	Low	Mid conf cloud
22144	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Mid	Low	Low	Low	Mid conf cloud over water
22280	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	High	Low	Low	Low	High conf Cloud
23888	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Low	High	Low	Low	High conf cloud shadow
23952	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Low	High	Low	Low	Water with cloud shadow
24088	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Mid	High	Low	Low	Mid conf cloud with shadow
24216	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Mid	High	Low	Low	Mid conf cloud with shadow over water
24344	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	High	High	Low	Low	High conf cloud with shadow
24472	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	High	High	Low	Low	High conf cloud with shadow over water
30048	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Low	Low	High	Low	High conf snow/ice
54596	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Low	Low	Low	High	High conf Cirrus
54852	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Mid	Low	Low	High	Cirrus, mid cloud
55052	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	High	Low	Low	High	Cirrus, high cloud

Table 1: Landsat 8 Pixel Quality Assessment (QA_PIXEL) value interpretations. The marked values are the target parameters that are retained in the converted QA files.

2.3 Final editing of the LST files

The following steps were carried out to obtain an LST map for the whole of Germany:

- For each tile and all available raster calculated with the preceding steps within these tiles calculation of the monthly mean values and then mean values stacking the 12 monthly mean values raster per tile using the ArcGIS Mosaic Raster tool.
- Cutting out the edges of the raster files with the average values (inaccuracies in the boundaries of the individual satellite images result in blurred edges, which affect the quality of the overall map).
- Merging all tiles with Mosaic Raster to create an LST map for the whole of Germany.

3. Results

To check whether the results correlate with the temperature values of the DWD (soil temperature at a depth of 5 cm), the temperature values from the calculated LST map were read out at the corresponding locations (ArcGIS tool Extract Values from Table) and the deviations between Landsat 8 and DWD were statistically evaluated.

The overall picture was good, but a few outliers resulted in a standard deviation of approximately 1.16. This can be attributed to the fact that Landsat 8 data is only recorded every 16 days, while the DWD values are based on daily measurements.

This means that significant temperature changes can occur between the times when the Landsat 8 data was recorded, which can affect the average value.

Figure 3: Deviation of the calculated LST from the ground temperatures (5 cm depth) at the DWD weather stations. Right: calculation using Landsat 8 data only; left: Landsat 8 and MODIS combined.

To estimate the magnitude of the influence on the average temperature, another data set was included in the LST map. This is the average temperature calculated using MODIS satellite data. The MODIS data has the advantage of being recorded daily, but at the same time has a significantly lower spatial resolution.

By incorporating the MODIS data, the result is an LST map that has the spatial resolution of the Landsat 8 data, but whose temporal resolution is now significantly improved. This improvement is reflected in a significantly lower standard deviation in the difference between Landsat 8 LST and DWD temperatures (see figure 4).

Figure 4: Left – Deviation of the differences between the calculated Landsat 8 LST and ground temperatures at a depth of 5 cm at the DWD measuring stations. Right – Deviation of the differences between the calculated Landsat 8 LST incorporating MODIS and ground temperatures at a depth of 5 cm at the DWD measuring stations.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the use of Landsat 8 satellite data allows comprehensive LST to be generated with very good spatial resolution. On the other hand, the temporal resolution can lead to deviations. Merging Landsat 8 data with other satellite data has the potential to offset the disadvantages of temporal resolution. Following this initial step, work is now underway on further developing the process in order to obtain even more accurate LST values by merging Landsat 8 and MODIS data.

These results are incorporated into the approximation of the temperature-depth profile of boreholes (Delfs et al., in press) with the aim of investigating whether this can serve to accelerate the evaluation process.

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